

		Standard Operating Procedure SOP-AVITHRAPID
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Version:	1	
Valid from:	2026-05-20	

	Created by	Controlled by	Approved by
Name	Ilenia Varasi	Francesco Saladini	Maurizio Zazzi
Email	ilenia.varasi@student.unisi.it	saladini6@unisi.it	maurizio.zazzi@unisi.it
Date	05/02/2026	05/02/2026	04/03/2026

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1. Purpose

This Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) defines the method for evaluating the cytotoxicity of test compounds within the AVITHRAPID project using a luminescence-based cell viability assay.

2. Scope

This SOP applies to *in vitro* cytotoxicity testing performed on mammalian cell lines to support the selection of non-cytotoxic concentrations for the screening of antiviral activity in cell-based assays.

3. Responsibilities

3.1. Laboratory Personnel

Personnel are responsible for correct execution of the cytotoxicity assay, preparation of reagents, and documentation of results.

3.2. Study Manager

The Study Manager ensures proper review and approval of cytotoxicity data

4. Materials and Equipment

4.1. Cell Lines

Cytotoxicity assays may be performed using the following mammalian cell lines, depending on the experimental objectives:

- Huh-7 human hepatoma cells (#JCRB0403 from JCRB Cell Bank)
- A549-hACE2-TMPRSS2 cell line (#a549-hace2tpsa from InvivoGen)
- VERO E6 cells (#CRL-1586 from ATCC)

4.2. Reagents and Materials

- DMEM High Glucose (cod. ECM0728L, Euroclone) supplemented with Fetal Bovine Serum South America origin EU 1% (cod. ECS5000L, Euroclone), Penicillin/Streptomycin 1% (cod. ECB3001D, Euroclone), referred to as “complete DMEM”
- DMSO 100% (cod. 472301, Sigma) as solvent control
- Reference compounds: Sofosbuvir (cod. HY-15005, DBA), Nirmatrelvir (cod. HY-138687, DBA)

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- P-gp inhibitor CP-100356 hydrochloride (cat. HY-108347, DBA)
- Test Compound(s)
- CellTiter-Glo® 2.0 (cod. G9242, Promega)
- White 96-well plates suitable for luminescence detection
- Adjustable pipettes and sterile consumables

4.3. Equipment

- CO₂ incubator (37°C, 5% CO₂)
- Class II biological safety cabinet
- Phase contrast microscope
- GloMax® Discover Microplate Reader (Promega)
- Orbital shaker

5. Procedure

5.1. Cell Seeding

Cells are seeded in 96-well plates at a defined density specific to each cell line (Huh-7, A549-AT, or VERO E6) and incubated overnight at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂ to allow proper cell adhesion and stabilization.

5.2. Compound Treatment

5.2.1. Huh-7 Cell Line Protocol

- On Day 0, Huh-7 cells (6,000 cells/well) are seeded in 96-well plates in complete DMEM and incubated at 37°C, 5% CO₂. In the late afternoon, a pre-incubation protocol is initiated by adding serial dilutions of investigational compounds: a six-point serial fold-4 dilution of the compounds is prepared starting from 200 µM.
- Sofosbuvir is included as the reference compound starting from 200 µM. Investigational compounds are serially diluted starting from 200 µM, or from lower concentrations when limited by compound availability. Untreated cells represent the 100% viability control, while cells exposed to 100% DMSO represent the 0% viability control. Additional wells are exposed to serial dilutions of DMSO to match solvent concentrations present in compound dilutions.
- Plates are incubated for 16 hours at 37°C, 5% CO₂.
- On Day 1, compound-containing medium is removed and replaced with DMEM 1% FBS for 1 hour to mimic viral adsorption conditions. Medium is then removed and freshly

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prepared compound dilutions or control media are added. Plates are incubated for 72 hours, 5% CO₂.

- On Day 3, cell viability is assessed using the CellTiter-Glo® 2.0 assay as described in Section 6.3.

5.2.2. A549-AT Cell Line Protocol

- On Day 0, A549-AT cells or VERO E6 cells are seeded at 6,000 cells/well in 96-well plates in complete DMEM and incubated at 37°C, 5% CO₂. In the late afternoon, pre-incubation with investigational compounds is initiated: A six-point serial fold-4 dilution of investigational compounds is prepared starting from 100 µM.
- Nirmatrelvir is used as the reference compound starting from 100 µM. Six wells of untreated cells are used as the 100% viability control, while three wells exposed to 100% DMSO serve as the 0% viability control. Additional wells are exposed to four serial dilutions of DMSO to simulate solvent concentrations present in compound dilutions.
- Plates are incubated for 16 hours at 37°C, 5% CO₂.
- On Day 1, compound dilutions are removed. Freshly prepared compound and reference compound dilutions are added in the presence of a defined volume of medium to mimic viral adsorption conditions. Untreated growth medium is added to control wells. Plates are incubated for 72 hours at 37°C, 5% CO₂.
- On Day 3, cell viability is measured as described in Section 6.3.

5.2.3. VERO E6 Cell Line Protocol

- On Day 0, VERO E6 cells (6,000 cells/well) are seeded in 96-well plates in complete DMEM and incubated at 37 °C and 5% CO₂ to allow cell adhesion.
- On Day 1, freshly prepared investigational compounds are added directly to the cells for a 1-hour pre-incubation. A six-point serial 4-fold dilution is prepared starting from 100 µM.
- The P-glycoprotein efflux inhibitor CP-100356 is added at the predefined working concentration (0.5 µM) together with the investigational compounds to inhibit cellular efflux mechanisms. Nirmatrelvir is included as the reference compound. Untreated cells and cells exposed to 100% DMSO are used as positive and negative controls of cell viability, respectively. Additional DMSO dilution-matched controls are included to reflect the DMSO concentrations present in compound dilutions.
- After the 1-hour pre-incubation, a defined volume of DMEM is added to each well to mimic viral addition conditions in the antiviral assay, without removing the compound-containing medium. Plates are then incubated at 37 °C and 5% CO₂ for 72 hours.

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- On Day 3, cell viability is measured as described in Section 6.3.

5.3. Cell Viability Measurement

At the selected time point, cell viability is measured using the CellTiter-Glo® 2.0 assay according to the manufacturer's instructions.

- The growth medium is carefully removed from each well to avoid disturbing the cell monolayer.
- An appropriate volume of CellTiter-Glo® 2.0 reagent (60 µL) is then added directly to each well.
- Plates are placed on an orbital shaker (400 rpm) and incubated for 10 minutes at room temperature, protected from light, to allow complete cell lysis and stabilization of the luminescent signal generated by the ATP-dependent luciferase reaction.
- The resulting lysate is transferred (50 µL) to a white 96-well luminescence plate suitable for signal detection.
- Luminescence is measured using the GloMax® Discover Microplate Reader (Promega) with instrument settings optimized for CellTiter-Glo assays.
- Relative luminescence units (RLUs) are recorded for each well and used for subsequent data normalization and calculation of cytotoxicity parameters.

6. Data Analysis

6.1. Data Processing

Raw luminescence data are exported from the GloMax® Discover Microplate Reader and processed using GraphPad Prism software.

For each experimental plate:

- The blank value (background signal) is subtracted from all measured relative luminescence unit (RLU) values.
- The mean RLU value of untreated cell control wells is defined as representing 100% cell viability.
- The mean RLU value of wells exposed to 100% DMSO is defined as representing 0% cell viability.

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6.2. Cytotoxicity Parameters

Dose–response curves are generated by plotting the percentage of cell viability versus the logarithm of compound concentration. Using non-linear regression analysis, the half-maximal cytotoxic concentration (CC_{50}) and the highest concentration associated with >90% cell viability are calculated using GraphPad software v.9.0.

7. Acceptance Criteria

Results are considered acceptable if all of the following conditions are met:

- The mean RLU value of the 100% viability control wells is at least 2–3 logarithmic units higher than the mean RLU value of the 0% viability control wells.
- The difference in cell viability among replicates at each compound concentration does not exceed 20% within the same experimental run.

8. Documentation and Archiving

All raw data and calculated CC_{50} values are recorded and archived according to internal procedures.

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9. Annexes

9.1. Plate layout

